

Statistical analysis plan to compare efficacy of endTB regimens and 6BPaLM for PLHIV

Nima S. Hejazi

Michael D. Hughes

Carole D. Mitnick

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1 Background

This project proposes the development and implementation of a unified causal, statistical, and data-analytic approach to facilitate the direct comparison of therapeutic efficacy across several investigational, all-oral regimens recently studied in two randomized controlled clinical trials (RCTs) of multidrug- and rifampin-resistant (MDR/RR-) TB therapeutics—endTB and TB-PRACTECAL, both sponsored by Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF). Direct comparison of a subset of the regimens studied in these two recently completed RCTs is necessary to inform normative guidance and clinical practice in the treatment of MDR/RR-TB, for which a 2024 WHO Rapid Communication recommended eight all-oral regimens, four of which were studied in endTB and TB-PRACTECAL ([WHO Global Programme on Tuberculosis and Lung Health, 2024](#)). While TB is the leading infectious killer of humans, MDR/RR-TB presents a particularly stark case, with approximately a half-million new cases occurring annually and limited treatment options, all backed by low certainty of evidence. Given the limited and low-certainty evidence available, WHO recommends use of the shortest regimen (6BPaLM) in place of longer, reinforced MDR/RR-TB regimens (9BLMZ, 9BCLLZ, and 9BDLLfxZ), but such a recommendation is not based on direct comparison and may not be suitable for immunocompromised groups with elevated risk, such as people living with HIV (PLHIV), who, in particular, have been found to have elevated risk of TB recurrence and poor outcomes under standard treatments. Currently, there is no evidence to suggest that the all-oral shortened regimens

recommended by WHO work equally well for PLHIV as for the general population. Furthermore, given the severely limited and precarious nature of funding for TB research, it is highly unlikely that a new RCT will be conducted to address this question. Thus, we propose to undertake an analytical study to shed light on this issue.

In order to directly compare the MDR/RR-TB regimens of interest, we will draw upon cutting-edge causal-analytic and statistical frameworks to quantify therapeutic efficacy. We will also emphasize the role of estimands that are sensitive to effect heterogeneity in order to characterize how efficacy in the broader at-risk population may differ from that experienced by PLHIV. This study is possible because endTB and TB-PRACTECAL included PLHIV, breaking from past norm of enrollment in TB trials; both RCTs succeeded in recruiting a moderate number of PLHIV as study participants.

2 Approach

The endTB phase 3 noninferiority RCT ([Guglielmetti et al., 2021](#); [Guglielmetti et al., 2025](#)) evaluated six (including standard-of-care) therapeutic regimens for MDR/RR-TB, five of which were 9-month, all-oral investigational regimens. The endTB RCT was conducted across seven countries—Georgia, India, Kazakhstan, Lesotho, Pakistan, Peru, and South Africa—and used multiple, local definitions of standard-of-care, including 18-20-month all-oral individualized regimens ([WHO Global Programme on Tuberculosis and Lung Health, 2025](#)). TB-PRACTECAL was a phase 2/3, noninferiority RCT ([Nyang’wa et al., 2022, 2024](#)) that examined three 6-month, all-oral investigational therapeutic regimens for MDR/RR-TB against standard-of-care. The TB-PRACTECAL RCT was conducted across three countries—South Africa, Belarus, and Uzbekistan—and, like endTB, used multiple, local definitions of standard-of-care, including both 9-12-month and 18-20-month all-oral regimens ([WHO Global Programme on Tuberculosis and Lung Health, 2025](#)).

The proposed analyses will provide a comparative evaluation of the therapeutic efficacy of *three* 9-month endTB regimens (9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, 9BDLLfxZ) versus a *single* 6-month TB-PRACTECAL regimen (6BPaLM)—see refs ([Guglielmetti et al., 2021](#); [Nyang’wa et al., 2022, 2024](#); [Guglielmetti et al., 2025](#)) for specifics on each of the regimens—focusing on PLHIV. These regimens have been selected for comparison because they have been recommended by WHO for the treatment of rifampin-resistant, fluoroquinolone-susceptible TB ([WHO Global Programme on Tuberculosis and Lung Health, 2025](#), see Table B). Specifically, the aims are to

1. (Aim 1) Designing and implementing statistical analyses to compare the efficacy of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLZ, and 9BDLLfxZ against 6BPaLM in PLHIV by using targeted learning methodology to analyze the data from the emulated trial ([van der Laan and Rubin, 2006](#); [van der Laan and Rose, 2011, 2018](#)). This will be achieved by assessing the efficacy of the investigational regimens in the PLHIV subcohort of the observational study (emulated trial) via targeted maximum likelihood estimation of the average treatment effect (ATE) in the PLHIV target population.
2. (Aim 2) Characterizing potential effect modification of therapeutic efficacy of the four candidate regimens by HIV coinfection status, by implementing statistical approaches for stratified medicine. This necessitates evaluating effect modification by PLHIV versus non-PLwH status using marginal structural models ([Robins, 1999](#); [Robins, Hernán and Brumback, 2000](#); [Hernán, Brumback and Robins, 2001](#); [Neugebauer and van der Laan, 2007](#); [Hernán and Robins, 2025](#)) and nonparametric estimation of heterogeneous treatment effects based on the conditional

average treatment effect (CATE) (Robins, 2004; Luedtke and Laan, 2016; Kennedy, 2023; van der Laan, Carone and Luedtke, 2024).

Comparison of the four regimens independently evaluated across the endTB and TB-PRACTECAL RCTs using individual patient data (IPD) can be facilitated by target trial emulation, a framework that outlines key components of the RCTs and how these components must be aligned in order for any cross-study comparisons to be valid. Such RCT components include the primary outcome definition; exclusion criteria; adverse events (AEs), their scoring, and how study participants who experienced AEs were handled (e.g., disenrollment); start and end of follow-up, i.e., study participants' time-at-risk; loss to follow-up, e.g., death; and administrative censoring, including possible interruptions or even discontinuation of enrollment based on non-adherence to assigned treatment. While endTB and TB-PRACTECAL may be approximately aligned along several of these components, there are some aspects for which alignment may not be achieved to a satisfactory degree, most notably, geographic regions in study sites fell. By applying the target trial emulation framework, we will pool IPD across endTB and TB-PRACTECAL to emulate a target trial (hypothetical RCT) that, if conducted *de novo*, would satisfy the above desiderata and thereby accommodate valid direct, cross-trial comparisons of the four investigational therapeutic regimens of interest.

3 Target Trial Emulation

Table 1 below formulates an observational study (emulated trial) from the endTB and TB-PRACTECAL RCTs via the *target trial emulation* (TTE) framework (Hernán and Robins, 2016; Hernán et al., 2016; Hernán, Wang and Leaf, 2022; Hansford et al., 2023). We first specify a target trial—that is, an idealized, hypothetical RCT—and subsequently map its key features (including the aforementioned desiderata) to an emulated trial—that is, an observational study—to be carried out in its place. The target and emulated trials, both specified below, facilitate comparison of both safety and efficacy endpoints in comparing the three endTB regimens (9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, 9BDLLfxZ) of interest to the TB-PRACTECAL regimen (6BPaLM). Aim 1 specifies comparison in a PLHIV-only study population, which corresponds to a target trial with PLHIV study participants. In Aim 2, we propose an effect modification analysis, requiring the inclusion of non-PLHIV study participants as well and thus corresponding to another target trial, distinct from the first, with unrestricted enrollment of both PLHIV and non-PLHIV study participants. Thus, these comparisons require that the target trial emulation process be carried out separately for each aim. Importantly, note that target trial emulation, once carried out, yields a single dataset pooling IPD across both endTB and TB-PRACTECAL from an *emulated* trial. As the emulated trial does not carry the benefits conferred by randomization of treatment assignment, statistical analysis of the dataset of pooled IPD will require confounder adjustment, as noted in Table 1 and detailed in subsequent sections.

Table 1: Criteria for creating an emulated trial from the endTB and TB-PRACTECAL RCTs for a PLHIV study population (Aim 1).

	Target Trial (ideal)	Emulated Trial (real)
Eligibility criteria (baseline only)	<p>Inclusion</p> <p>age ≥ 15 rifampin-resistant fluoroquinolone-susceptible baseline labs grade ≤ 4 HIV seropositivity</p> <p>Exclusion</p> <p>pregnancy elevated liver enzymes QTcF ≥ 450msec uncorrectable electrolyte disorders on treatment for 2+ weeks investigator discretion</p>	same
Treatment strategies	6BPaLM 9BLMZ 9BCLLfxZ 9BDLLfxZ	same
Treatment assignment	randomly assigned (1:1:1:1) to each arm, stratified by country/region	<i>IPW</i> by key baseline covariates used for confounder adjustment
Time zero and follow-up	<i>time zero</i> : first dose initiation <i>follow-up</i> : ends at occurrence of primary endpoint, censoring, or administrative end of study	same, with 1-week grace period (72/73 weeks) for primary endpoint
Outcomes	WHO composite outcomes	same
Causal contrasts	<i>Three distinct pairwise contrasts:</i> ITT: 6BPaLM versus 9BLMZ ITT: 6BPaLM versus 9BCLLfxZ ITT: 6BPaLM versus 9BDLLfxZ	same, constructed as a single four-arm study
Statistical analysis	ITT analysis	same, with <i>IPCW</i> for censoring adjustment

4 Causal Model and Identification

4.1 Causal model

We consider data from the emulated trial as a collection of baseline confounders (e.g., characteristics of underlying trial populations) L , treatment assignment A , and outcome Y on n study units, denoting by $O = (L, A, Y)$ the data on a single study unit, of which we consider observing n copies, $O_1, \dots, O_n \sim \mathbb{P}_n$, where \mathbb{P}_n denotes the empirical distribution of the observed sample of study participants. We take $O \sim \mathbb{P}_0$ for \mathbb{P}_0 being the underlying data-generating law assumed only to lie in an unrestricted statistical model, $\mathbb{P}_0 \in \mathcal{M}$.¹ A structural causal model (SCM) (Pearl, 2009; Bareinboim et al., 2022), $\mathcal{C} = (U, O, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P}_U)$, may be used to express the process by which the data are generated:

$$\begin{aligned} L &= f_L(U_L) \\ A &= f_A(L, U_A) \\ Y &= f_Y(A, L, U_Y) , \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{F} = (f_L, f_A, f_Y)$ are deterministic but unknown functions that give rise to the corresponding variables in the system, $O = (L, A, Y)$, respectively, and $U = (U_L, U_A, U_Y)$ are *unmeasured* (or exogenous) error terms with joint distribution \mathbb{P}_U , which we will restrict via a mutual independence condition²—that is, $U_L \perp\!\!\!\perp U_A \perp\!\!\!\perp U_Y$ —to simplify identification. Counterfactual random variables, or potential outcomes, are generated by applying hypothetical interventions to the structural equations \mathcal{F} of the SCM \mathcal{C} ; for example, Y^a is generated by replacing f_A with $A = a$ (corresponding to a static intervention that *sets* A to a) and then replacing the pre-intervention output of f_A , A , in f_Y by the post-intervention value of the treatment, a . These potential outcomes define causal contrasts, such as the average treatment effect (ATE), $\theta_0^{\text{ATE}} = \mathbb{E}_0[Y^1 - Y^0]$, which is the target estimand in ITT analysis (Aim 1), and the conditional average treatment effect (CATE), $\theta_0^{\text{CATE}}(V) = \mathbb{E}_0[Y^1 - Y^0 \mid V]$, which acts as a measure of effect modification (Aim 2) by quantifying the degree to which the ATE varies across strata $v \in V$ defined by pre-intervention covariates V .³ Per Table 1, the causal contrasts that capture the scientific questions of Aims 1 and 2 consist of three pairwise contrasts (of 6BPaLM against each of the three endTB regimens); thus, the ATE and CATE, which are restricted by definition to contrasting binary treatments, may be used by performing three distinct analyses that operationalize the treatment in distinct ways: $A = 1$ representing one of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, or 9BDLLfxZ as appropriate and $A = 0$ representing 6BPaLM.

4.2 Identification

We require standard assumptions for the identification of θ_{ATE} (Pearl, 2009; Hernán and Robins, 2025):

1. no unmeasured confounding (exchangeability): $Y^a \perp\!\!\!\perp A \mid L$ for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$, and
2. positivity: $\mathbb{P}_0\{\mathbb{P}_0(A = a \mid L) > \epsilon\} = 1$ for some $\epsilon > 0$ and for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$.

¹Throughout, we will index by a subscript naught those quantities that reference the unknown data-generating law \mathbb{P}_0 and by an n subscript those derived from the empirical distribution \mathbb{P}_n .

²The condition of mutual independence of exogenous errors defines a non-parametric structural equation model with independent errors (NPSEM-IE).

³Note that the CATE and the ATE are closely related—specifically, $\sum_{v \in V} \theta_0^{\text{CATE}}(v) = \theta_0^{\text{ATE}}$ for V discrete.

Under these assumptions, the causal contrast θ_{ATE} may be re-expressed as ψ_{ATE} , which depends only on components of the observed data (that is, it is a statistical functional):

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_0^{\text{ATE}} &= \mathbb{E}_0[Y^1 - Y^0] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[Y^1 - Y^0 \mid L]\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[Y^1 \mid L] - \mathbb{E}_0[Y^0 \mid L]\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[Y^1 \mid A, L] - \mathbb{E}_0[Y^0 \mid A, L]\} \\ \psi_0^{\text{ATE}} &= \mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A = 1, L] - \mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A = 0, L]\},\end{aligned}$$

where the first two steps iterate the expectation operator and use linearity of expectation, the penultimate step uses no unmeasured confounding, and the final step invokes the consistency rule (Pearl, 2010); note that the positivity assumption is required throughout for the conditioning sets of the expectations to be well-defined. We will denote by $b_0(A, L)$ the conditional mean of the outcome $\mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A, L]$, so that ψ_0^{ATE} may be expressed $\psi_0^{\text{ATE}} = \mathbb{E}_0[b_0(1, L) - b_0(0, L)]$. From this identifying expression, estimation of ψ_0^{ATE} necessitates estimation of the outcome regression $b_0(A, L)$. This identifying expression yields a *plug-in estimator* of the ATE.

Under the same identification conditions, an alternative expression for ψ_0^{ATE} is possible:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_0^{\text{ATE}} &= \mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A = 1, L] - \mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A = 0, L]\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}_0\left\{\frac{\mathbb{E}_0[AY \mid L]}{\mathbb{P}_0(A = 1 \mid L)} - \frac{\mathbb{E}_0[(1 - A)Y \mid L]}{1 - \mathbb{P}_0(A = 1 \mid L)}\right\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}_0\left\{\frac{\mathbb{I}(A = 1)Y}{g_{A,0}(L)} - \frac{\mathbb{I}(A = 0)Y}{1 - g_{A,0}(L)}\right\},\end{aligned}$$

where $g_{A,0}(L) := \mathbb{P}_0(A = 1 \mid L)$ is the propensity score, and the step between the first and second lines applies the identity $\mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A = 1, L]\} \equiv \mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[AY \mid L]/\mathbb{P}_0(A = 1 \mid L)\}$. This latter expression can be used to construct *inverse probability weighted* (IPW) estimators.

The CATE is identified under conditions (Robins, 2004; VanderWeele et al., 2019; Kennedy, 2023) similar to those of the ATE. To clarify our previous definition of the CATE, consider the unit-level data structure $O = (L, A, Y)$ and partition the putative confounders L into candidate pre-treatment effect modifiers $V \subset L$ and the remainder of the confounder adjustment set $\{L \setminus V\}$. Recall that the CATE, a function of effect modifiers V , is defined

$$\theta_0^{\text{CATE}}(V) = \mathbb{E}_0[Y^1 - Y^0 \mid V], \quad (1)$$

where $\theta_0^{\text{CATE}}(V)$ is a function of the candidate effect modifiers V . Thus, $\theta_0^{\text{CATE}}(V = v)$ may be interpreted as the effect of treatment A on the outcome Y in the stratum $V = v$. In the present context, V is an indicator of PLHIV status at baseline. Importantly, note that $\theta_0^{\text{CATE}}(V = v)$ uses for confounder adjustment all putative confounders $\{L \setminus V\}$ across both PLHIV and non-PLHIV study units, thus easing justification of the exchangeability assumption relative to the alternative case in which the analysis would be performed only in the PLHIV stratum.

By an identification argument similar to that used above for the ATE, the CATE function is identified as

$$\psi_0^{\text{CATE}}(V) = \mathbb{E}_0\{\mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A = 1, L] - \mathbb{E}_0[Y \mid A = 0, L] \mid V\}, \quad (2)$$

where $\psi_0^{\text{CATE}}(V)$ may be used to construct estimators based on this and/or analogous representations. A growing body of work has examined estimation of the CATE by applying supervised learning with

empirical risk minimization based on risk functions tailored to the CATE; these risk functions are derived from loss functions—for example, the DR-learner loss (Luedtke and Laan, 2016; Kennedy, 2023) and the R-learner loss (Nie and Wager, 2021)—that depend on unknown nuisance functions, posing challenges for estimation. Thus, estimation proceeds by first constructing estimators of the nuisance functions relevant for the loss function, then applying empirical risk minimization with the estimated nuisance functions, which, under regularity conditions, performs as well as the oracle empirical risk minimization with the true nuisance functions. We will use the DR-learner, which is based on a loss function with a doubly robust (DR) pseudo-outcome, to construct an estimator of $\psi_0^{\text{CATE}}(V)$; should the DR-learner prove unstable, we will explore use of the more recently proposed EP-learner (van der Laan et al., 2024), whose robustness properties provide it an advantage over the DR-learner in certain settings.

An alternative measure of effect modification, distinct from the non-parametric definition of the CATE, can be based upon a marginal structural model (MSM) (Robins, 1999; Robins et al., 2000; Hernán et al., 2001). An MSM is akin to a standard regression model (Greenland, 2024), with the key difference being that the regression function (the left-hand side, to which a model is applied) involves counterfactuals while the regression model (the right-hand side, which postulates a functional form) involves only factual random variables. For the study of effect modification, MSMs of the following form have been proposed (Hernán and Robins, 2025):

$$\mathbb{E}_0[Y^a \mid V] = \beta_0 + \beta_1 a + \beta_2 Va + \beta_3 V. \quad (3)$$

In Equation 3, fitting of the MSM is performed with inverse probability of treatment and censoring weights (detailed in the next sections). The parameter β_2 of the MSM measures modification of the effect of A on Y by V . The non-parametric definition of the CATE (Equation 1) yields the ATE after marginalization with respect to the distribution of putative effect modifiers V ; this applies to the MSM formulation as well, though recovery of the ATE may be challenging when V is not discrete. To see this, note that the ATE, expressed in terms of the parameters of this MSM (Equation 3), $(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3)$, is a function of both β_1 and β_2 . Per Hernán and Robins (2025), while the MSM of Equation 3 is referred to, by convention, as a *marginal* structural model, it is, in fact, *conditional* on V .

4.3 Confounder adjustment by IPTW

Inverse probability of treatment weighting (IPTW) can be used to adjust for confounding of the treatment-outcome relationship by baseline covariates, or putative confounders, L . The IPTW-based strategy addresses confounding of the A - Y relationship by L by reweighting study units such that the treatment assignment (after reweighting) is independent of baseline covariates $A \perp\!\!\!\perp L$; this may intuitively be thought of as artificially constructing a pseudo-population in which treatment groups are exchangeable $Y^a \perp\!\!\!\perp A$ after reweighting based on putative confounders (Hernán and Robins, 2025). Note that this form of exchangeability is similar to what randomization of treatment assignment achieves when perfectly implemented, that is, $Y^a \perp\!\!\!\perp A$, though randomization achieves this without need for reweighting. While IPTW can enforce exchangeability in this manner, its success in doing so depends crucially on both the set of putative confounders being complete (that is, no unmeasured confounders) and the quality of the modeling procedure used to construct IPTW weights. In practice, this may be empirically evaluated by sensitivity analyses but is otherwise an untestable assumption. For validity and reproducibility of an analysis, the set of putative confounders should be pre-specified. In order to best achieve this, we have developed the following

list of patient-level *baseline covariates to be used for confounder adjustment*—study region, BMI, diabetes status, disease severity (a composite of cavitation and smear), pyrazinamide resistance, and HIV serostatus (Aim 2 only). Our list is based on considerations including clinical input and the cross-trial availability of specific covariates.

The use of IPTW in estimation requires the construction of inverse weights based on the propensity score⁴—that is, the probability of being assigned treatment $A = a$ (one of 6BPaLM, 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, and 9BDLLfxZ), given baseline covariates L . As the propensity score is an unknown function of the data, an estimator, $g_{A,n}(L) := \mathbb{P}_n(A = a \mid L)$, must be constructed in order to adjust for confounding by baseline covariates. Often, the estimator $g_{A,n}(L)$ of the propensity score is based on parametric regression modeling via, for example, logistic regression (Hernán and Robins, 2025), though more flexible machine learning or non-parametric regression procedures may be applied instead (e.g., van der Laan and Rose, 2011). After obtaining an estimate of the propensity score, such an estimate may be used to construct inverse probability (IP) of treatment weights as $\mathbb{1}(A = a)/g_{A,n}(L)$.

4.4 Censoring adjustment by IPCW

Over the course of the endTB and TB-PRACTECAL RCTs, several patients were lost to follow-up (i.e., without measured endpoint by 72/73 weeks); thus, we expect the emulated trial data to similarly feature this and other forms of censoring. Above, we defined the observed data as $O = (L, A, Y)$, which rules out the possibility of censoring C . To address this complication, let us expand the definition of our observed data unit to $O = (L, A, C, CY)$, where $C \in \{0, 1\}$ is an indicator of censoring and let $C = 1$ denote that the given study unit O was *not* censored (that is, was observed), so that $CY = Y$.

To address possible selection bias due to censoring, we apply inverse probability of censoring weighting (IPCW) (van der Laan and Rose, 2011; Hernán and Robins, 2025), which enforces exchangeability of censoring status C and the potential outcomes $Y^{a,c=1}$, conditional on treatment and baseline covariates L , that is, $Y^{a,c=1} \perp\!\!\!\perp (A, C) \mid L$ ⁵. Conceptually, use of IPCW is analogous to that of IPTW, though the goal is to mitigate selection bias resulting from censoring. Notably, the censoring mechanism may depend on measured factors beyond the treatment and baseline covariates, including post-treatment variables, and the assumptions previously stated may be adjusted to reflect this. IPC weights can be constructed as $\mathbb{1}(C = 1)/g_{C,0}(A, L)$, where $g_{C,0}(A, L) := \mathbb{P}_0(C = 1 \mid A, L)$, the probability of *not being censored* (that is, of being observed), conditional on (A, L) . As with IPT weights, IPC weights require estimation of the censoring mechanism $g_{C,0}(A, L)$, for example, via logistic regression or more flexible regression strategies; denote by $g_{C,n}(A, L) := \mathbb{P}_n(C = 1 \mid A, L)$ a given estimator of $g_{C,0}(A, L)$. After estimation of the censoring mechanism, the estimates may be used to construct IPC weights of the form $\mathbb{1}(C = 1)/g_{C,n}(A, L)$, which may be used in conjunction with IPT weights. As before, it is critical to pre-specify the adjustment set for this step. To this end, we have developed the following list of patient-level *covariates to be used for censoring adjustment*—study region; BMI; diabetes status; disease severity (a composite of cavitation and smear); HIV serostatus (Aim 2 only); and *adverse events of special interest* (AESIs; grade 3 or higher), including hepatotoxicity, optic neuritis, peripheral neuropathy, prolonged QT, leukopenia,

⁴Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983) defined the propensity score as the coarsest function of L such that exchangeability of the treatment assignment A and potential outcomes Y^a holds conditionally, that is, $Y^a \perp\!\!\!\perp A \mid g_{A,0}(L)$.

⁵A similar, though less restrictive, assumption that censoring of the outcome results from a missing-at-random (MAR) censoring mechanism, $Y \perp\!\!\!\perp C \mid A, L$, may also be used.

anemia, and thrombocytopenia. Our list is based on considerations including clinical input and prior analyses. Adjustment for AESIs in this step draws on a particular strength in the design of endTB and TB-PRACTECAL—the coordination of pharmacovigilance strategies and definitions, made possible by the trials sharing a sponsor (MSF). Note that AESIs are measured post-randomization variables used for censoring adjustment, though we have, for simplicity, elected not to extend our notation to reflect their occurring post-randomization.

5 Estimation Strategy

5.1 Initial estimation of nuisance functions

We have thus far discussed the rationale for estimating three types of nuisance functions: the propensity score $g_{A,0}(L)$, the censoring mechanism $g_{C,0}(A, L)$, and the outcome regression $b_0(A, L)$. We have used naught subscripts to denote these quantities under the data-generating law P_0 and the n subscript to denote corresponding estimators. As noted, absent knowledge about the functional forms of these nuisance functions, it is generally preferable to employ machine learning or non-parametric regression strategies for their estimation. Given the large variety of statistical learning procedures available for such tasks, we opt for a strategy that does not require committing to a single algorithm or family of algorithms.

We will use the super learner algorithm (van der Laan, Polley and Hubbard, 2007), a form of ensemble modeling, or stacking (Wolpert, 1992; Breiman, 1996), that carries optimality guarantees derived from the framework of cross-validated loss-based estimation (van der Laan, Dudoit and Keles, 2004; Dudoit and van der Laan, 2005; van der Vaart, Dudoit and van der Laan, 2006), to learn a (nuisance) regression function—one of $g_{A,0}(L)$, $g_{C,0}(A, L)$, $b_0(A, L)$ —using a pre-specified library of candidate learning algorithms (that is, the so-called “ensemble” super learner procedure). The ensemble super learner incorporates a meta-learning step to appropriately weight predictions from candidate algorithms included in the library. Phillips et al. (2023) provide some recommendations for selecting algorithms and tuning super learner prediction models.

While we may, in principle, specify different libraries for the three nuisance parameter estimators $g_{A,n}(L)$, $g_{C,n}(A, L)$, and $b_n(A, L)$, we propose, as an initial step, to adopt a single library that includes variants of logistic regression, with main terms only and 2-way interactions; random forests, varying the number of trees and the sampling fraction (Breiman, 2001); gradient boosting machines (Friedman, 2001), varying the boosting iterations, tree depth, learning rate, and, optionally, the ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 regularization (Chen and Guestrin, 2016); several variants of elastic net regularization (Zou and Hastie, 2003), including both the lasso (Tibshirani, 1996) and ridge (Hoerl and Kennard, 1970) regression; and the highly adaptive lasso estimator (van der Laan, 2015).

When constructing an efficient estimator of a statistical functional, cross-fitting is routinely used both to reduce possible overfitting and to avoid the need for certain regularity conditions (Zheng and van der Laan, 2011; Chernozhukov et al., 2018). In order to employ cross-fitting, consider a partitioning of the index set $\{1, \dots, n\}$ into K non-overlapping subsets (or “folds”); that is, with respect to a given validation fold V_k , we can write $V_k \subset \{1, \dots, n\}$, $\cup_{k=1}^K V_k = \{1, \dots, n\}$, and $V_k \cap V_{k'} = \emptyset$ for $k \neq k'$. For a given V_k , define the corresponding training fold as $T_k = \{1, \dots, n\} \setminus V_k$; the training fold T_k will be used as input data with which to train a given learning algorithm (e.g., an ensemble super learner), with the predictions of the trained learning algorithm on the corresponding validation fold V_k being used as estimates of a given (nuisance) regression function for those units falling in

the subset V_k of the index set. After repeating the training-prediction process K times to exhaust each of the V_k validation folds, the estimate available for any given unit of the regression function in question will have originated only from an algorithm trained on a dataset from which the given unit was absent (that is, “holdout” predictions will be available for each unit and regression function).

5.2 Estimator construction

5.2.1 Evaluating the average treatment effect in the PLHIV cohort

In Aim 1, we propose assessing the efficacy of WHO-recommended investigational MDR/RR-TB regimens in PLHIV by emulating a target trial that restricts enrollment only to the PLHIV study population. After implementation of the trial emulation protocol (Table 1), we consider access to an observational (i.e., non-randomized) data set, $O_1, \dots, O_n \sim \mathbb{P}_n$, of n_{PLHIV} study units drawn from both the endTB and TB-PRACTECAL RCTs, where $O = (L, A, C, CY)$ as noted above and A is an indicator of treatment assigned (with $A = 1$ indicating one of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, and 9BDLLfxZ, and $A = 0$ indicating 6BPaLM). We consider estimating the ATE using two estimators: (1) an IPW estimator, $\psi_{n,\text{IPW}}^{\text{ATE}}$, that incorporates both IPTW and IPCW, and (2) a targeted maximum likelihood (TML) estimator, $\psi_{n,\text{TML}}^{\text{ATE}}$, that is based on the plug-in representation of the ATE and uses IPCW to adjust for censoring. The IPW estimator of the ATE is

$$\psi_{n,\text{IPW}}^{\text{ATE}} = \mathbb{E}_n \left\{ \frac{\mathbb{I}(C = 1)}{g_{C,n}(A, L)} \left[\left(\frac{\mathbb{I}(A = 1)}{g_{A,n}(L)} - \frac{\mathbb{I}(A = 0)}{1 - g_{A,n}(L)} \right) Y \right] \right\}, \quad (4)$$

which requires estimators of the propensity score $g_{A,n}(L)$ and the censoring mechanism $g_{C,n}(A, L)$, with the requirement that these estimators be based on parametric regression models. To fulfill this condition, we will use variants of logistic regression to estimate both $g_{A,n}(L)$ and $g_{C,n}(A, L)$. The IPW estimator may be constructed via the following series of steps.

1. Use logistic regression to construct an estimator of the propensity score $g_{A,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(A = 1 | L)$, for treatment being one of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, and 9BDLLfxZ. The functional form (right-hand side) specified should include main terms and two-way interactions of variables in the *treatment confounder adjustment set*. Obtain predictions from the fitted regression, denoting these $g_{A,n}$, for each study unit. Obtain also the additive inverse of these predictions, $1 - g_{A,n}$ for each study unit.
2. Use logistic regression to construct an estimator of the censoring mechanism $g_{C,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(C = 1 | A, L)$, where $C = 1$ indicates completion (i.e., not being censored). The functional form (right-hand side) specified should include main terms and two-way interactions of the treatment indicator and variables in the *censoring confounder adjustment set*. Obtain predictions from the fitted regression and denote these $g_{C,n}$. For censored study units (i.e., for whom $C = 0$), set their value of the outcome to zero; this is for bookkeeping purposes and will not affect subsequent calculations.
3. Compute the IPT weights as $\mathbb{I}(A = 1)/g_{A,n}$ and $\mathbb{I}(A = 0)/(1 - g_{A,n})$ for each study unit. Compute also the difference of these weights, $H_n(A, L) = (\mathbb{I}(A = 1)/g_{A,n}) - (\mathbb{I}(A = 0)/(1 - g_{A,n}))$ for each study unit.
4. Compute the IPC weights as $\mathbb{I}(C = 1)/g_{C,n}$ for each study unit.
5. Compute the IPW estimate of the ATE in Equation 4 by taking the mean of the product of the observed outcome Y , the difference of the IPT weights $H_n(A, L)$, and the IPC weights.

6. Compute also the IPW estimates of the absolute risk (that is, counterfactual risks comprising the two halves of the ATE) for the contrasts $A = 1$ and $A = 0$ by taking the mean of the product of the observed outcome Y , the appropriate IPT weights ($\mathbb{1}(A = 1)/g_{A,n}$ for the contrast $A = 1$ and $\mathbb{1}(A = 0)/(1 - g_{A,n})$ for the contrast $A = 0$), and the IPC weights.
7. Compute the standard errors of the IPW estimators based on the empirical variance of their corresponding estimating equations; alternatively, the non-parametric bootstrap may also be used (Hernán and Robins, 2025).
8. Repeat the process above for each choice of treatment, resulting in three IPW estimates of the ATE, one for each of the three causal contrasts specified in Table 1.

The TML estimator, by contrast, takes the form:

$$\psi_{n,\text{TML}}^{\text{ATE}} = \mathbb{E}_n[b_n^*(1, L) - b_n^*(0, L)] , \quad (5)$$

where $b_n^*(A, L)$ is an estimator of the outcome regression $b_n(A, L)$ that is fluctuated (or tilted) to act as a solution to a score term that appears in an efficient estimating equation (the efficient influence function; see Equation 7). This may be achieved by applying a univariate regression:

$$\text{logit}(b_n^*(A, L)) = \text{logit}(b_n(A, L)) + \epsilon H_n(A, L) ,$$

where $\text{logit}(b_n(A, L))$ is taken as an offset and the parameter ϵ of this one-dimensional model can be estimated by maximum likelihood. The term $H_n(A, L)$ is a component of the efficient influence function (EIF), $\chi^{\text{ATE}}(X; \mathbf{P})$, of the ATE functional, ψ_0^{ATE} , for the data unit X and at the law \mathbf{P} :

$$\chi^{\text{ATE}}(X; \mathbf{P}) = H_n(A, L)\{Y - b_n(A, L)\} + (b_n(1, L) - b_n(0, L)) - \psi_n^{\text{ATE}} , \quad (6)$$

where we introduce $X = (L, A, Y)$ to denote the *uncensored* data unit—that is, $O = (C, CX)$. This auxiliary covariate, $H_n(A, L)$, depends on the IPT weights previously discussed; it takes the form:

$$H_n(A, L) = \left(\frac{\mathbb{1}(A = 1)}{g_{A,n}(L)} - \frac{\mathbb{1}(A = 0)}{1 - g_{A,n}(L)} \right) .$$

Note that the TML estimator requires as ingredients estimators of all three of the nuisance functions introduced, that is, $g_{A,n}(L)$, $g_{C,n}(A, L)$, and $b_n(A, L)$, but, importantly, allows for arbitrary modeling procedures to be used for construction of these estimators. For the TML estimator, we propose to use a combination of cross-fitting and ensemble super learning to construct the nuisance estimators. Additionally, the TML estimator is *asymptotically semiparametric-efficient* (van der Laan and Rubin, 2006), meaning that it attains variance better than the IPW estimator is capable of achieving. This translates to both more sensitive hypothesis tests and narrower confidence intervals. Importantly, IPC weights must be multiplied by the auxiliary covariate, $H_n(A, L)$. Accounting for censoring, the EIF, $\chi^{\text{ATE}}(O; \mathbf{P})$, for the data unit O and at the law \mathbf{P} is

$$\chi^{\text{ATE}}(O; \mathbf{P}) = \frac{\mathbb{1}(C = 1)}{g_{C,n}(A, L)} H_n(A, L)\{Y - b_n(A, L)\} + (b_n(1, L) - b_n(0, L)) - \psi_n^{\text{ATE}} . \quad (7)$$

The TML estimator may be constructed via the following series of steps.

1. Split the data into K folds, repeating the process outlined below in Steps 2-4 on each of the training-validation splits in sequence, always performing any model fitting on a training fold and obtaining predictions only for the corresponding validation fold. We suppress notation to represent the folds for the sake of brevity.

2. Fit a super learner ensemble model to estimate $g_{A,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(A = 1 \mid L)$, the probability of receiving treatment (one of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, 9BDLLfxZ); the super learner should include as candidate algorithms a subset of those specified above (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting) as well as the exact form of the logistic regression model used to compute $g_{A,n}$ for the IPW estimator. All covariates specified in the treatment confounder adjustment set should be included. Obtain predictions from the fitted ensemble model and denote these $g_{A,n}$. Obtain also the additive inverse of these predictions, $1 - g_{A,n}$ for each study unit.
3. Fit a super learner ensemble model to estimate $g_{C,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(C = 1 \mid A, L)$, the probability of completion (i.e., not being censored); the super learner should include as candidate algorithms a subset of those specified above (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting) as well as the exact form of the logistic regression model used to compute $g_{C,n}$ for the IPW estimator. All covariates specified in the censoring confounder adjustment set should be included. Obtain predictions from the fitted ensemble model and denote these $g_{C,n}$. For study units that are censored (i.e., $C = 0$), set their value of the outcome to zero; this will have no bearing on downstream estimation.
4. Subset the training set to only those units that are uncensored, i.e., for whom $C = 1$, and fit a super learner ensemble model to estimate $b_n(A, L)$, the conditional mean of the outcome (e.g., the conditional probability of recurrence-free survival); the super learner should include as candidate algorithms a subset of those specified above (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting). Only covariates specified in the treatment confounder adjustment set should be included. Obtain predictions from the fitted ensemble model for *all units in the validation set* (i.e., regardless of censoring status) on three distinct datasets: the observed data and two counterfactual datasets. To do so, obtain predictions on all (validation) units under their observed treatment status ($A = a$) as well as under two counterfactual scenarios, the first in which all units are set to the treatment condition ($A = 1$) and the second where all units are set to the control condition ($A = 0$), denoting these three sets of predictions by $b_n(a, L)$, $b_n(1, L)$, and $b_n(0, L)$, respectively.
5. At this stage, collect predictions for each of the nuisance parameters across all study units, collating predictions across the K validation sets, V_1, \dots, V_K , to have holdout predictions of each nuisance parameter for each study unit.
6. Compute the targeting update in a “pooled” fashion (i.e., without any further sample splitting) by fitting a one-dimensional logistic regression model as noted above, using an initial estimate of the outcome regression as an offset and an auxiliary covariate defined as the product of the IPT and IPC weights, as indicated in Equation 7 above. Denote the updated estimates produced by this step as $b_n^*(1, L)$ and $b_n^*(0, L)$.
7. Compute the TML estimate of the ATE as the mean of the difference of the updated outcome regression estimates, as indicated in Equation 5, and its standard error based on the empirical variance of the estimated EIF, as given in Equation 7.
8. Compute also the TML estimates of the absolute risk (each half of the ATE) for the two contrasts $A = 1$ and $A = 0$ as the mean of the updated outcome regression estimate $b_n^*(1, L)$ and $b_n^*(0, L)$, respectively. Note that these updated outcome regression estimates ought to be adjusted such that they are targeted for the appropriate counterfactual risk rather than for the ATE as described above.
9. Repeat the process above for each choice of treatment, resulting in three TML estimates of the ATE, one for each of the three causal contrasts specified in Table 1.

5.2.2 Assessing effect modification via an MSM and the CATE

In Aim 2, we proposed evaluating evidence for effect modification in PLHIV of the efficacy of the WHO-recommended MDR/RR-TB regimens by emulating a target trial that enrolled from the at-risk population, regardless of PLHIV status. After implementation of the trial emulation protocol (Table 1), we consider having access to a data set, $O_1, \dots, O_n \sim P_n$, of n study units drawn from both the endTB and TB-PRACTECAL RCTs, where $O = (L, A, C, CY)$, $V \subset L$ is an indicator of membership in the PLHIV group, and A is one of 6BPaLM, 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, and 9BDLLfxZ. We consider estimating the CATE function, $\psi_0^{\text{CATE}}(V)$, using two approaches: (1) via an MSM (Equation 3) that uses IPTW and IPCW to adjust for baseline confounding and post-treatment censoring; and (2) a DR-learner (Luedtke and Laan, 2016; Kennedy, 2023; Pryce et al., 2024), which is based on a loss function tailored to estimation of the CATE function and uses an EIF, closely related to Equation 7, for the risk of estimating $\psi_0^{\text{CATE}}(V)$. Next, we outline implementations of both of these approaches.

An MSM, as given in Equation 3, can be formulated to evaluate evidence for modification of the treatment effect by putative effect modifiers V . As noted by Hernán and Robins (2025) (see Sec. 12.5), such an MSM does not, contrary to its name, target a marginal effect but instead recovers the conditional effect $\mathbb{E}[Y^a | V]$ and may be implemented by fitting a regression of the outcome Y on treatment A and effect modifiers V while incorporating both IPTW and IPCW in the fitting procedure (e.g., via weighted OLS). Implementation of such an MSM may be achieved as follows

1. Use logistic regression to construct an estimator of the propensity score $g_{A,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(A = 1 | L)$, for treatment being one of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, and 9BDLLfxZ. The functional form (right-hand side) specified should include main terms and two-way interactions of variables in the *treatment confounder adjustment set*. Importantly, the adjustment set should include V , PLHIV status. Obtain predictions from the fitted regression, denoting these $g_{A,n}$, for each study unit.
2. Use logistic regression to construct an estimator of the censoring mechanism $g_{C,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(C = 1 | A, L)$, where $C = 1$ indicates completion (i.e., not being censored). The functional form (right-hand side) specified should include main terms and two-way interactions of the treatment indicator and variables in the *censoring confounder adjustment set*. Obtain predictions from the fitted regression and denote these $g_{C,n}$. For censored study units (i.e., for whom $C = 0$), set their value of the outcome to zero.
3. For each unit, compute the IPT weight as $\mathbb{1}(A = 1)/g_{A,n}$ and the IPC weight as $\mathbb{1}(C = 1)/g_{C,n}$.
4. Fit the MSM as in Equation 3 by regressing the observed outcome Y on the treatment A and effect modifier V , using weighted OLS to incorporate inverse probability weights computed as the product of the IPT and IPC weights (Hernán and Robins, 2025, see Sec. 12.5 and 12.6).

In the present context, where the treatment A is an indicator of receiving either 6BPaLM or one of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfxZ, and 9BDLLfxZ and the effect modifier V is an indicator of PLHIV status, a saturated MSM may be constructed in the final step above, allowing for straightforward estimation of the MSM parameters and, correspondingly, inference on effect modification by V , provided accurate estimation of the IPT and IPC weights. As with the IPW estimator of the ATE previously discussed, the MSM approach to effect modification suffers from drawbacks including the need for consistent estimation of the IPT and IPC weights by restrictive regression procedures prone to misspecification bias and diminished interpretability when the MSM is not a saturated model in A and V . As an alternative to this approach, we consider assessing treatment effect heterogeneity via a DR-learner (Luedtke and Laan, 2016; Kennedy, 2023).

Estimation of the CATE function via a DR-learner approach has been extensively studied in the causal/de-biased machine learning literature. By allowing for regularized regression and flexible machine learning techniques to be incorporated into the estimation process, the DR-learner, and related methods, overcome some of the aforementioned drawbacks of MSMs. The DR-learner algorithm, one among several approaches proposed for estimation of $\psi_0^{\text{CATE}}(V)$, proceeds by constructing a doubly robust pseudo-outcome (Rubin and Laan, 2007) based on the EIF of the risk of the CATE function (Kennedy, 2023; van der Laan et al., 2024), and then regresses this *estimated* pseudo-outcome, which depends on estimated nuisance functions, on the putative effect modifiers V . Estimation details have been discussed in the literature; saliently, Pryce et al. (2024) outline considerations for application of the DR-learner with data subject to missingness in the outcome of interest (see their Algorithm 1). Implementation of a DR-learner for estimation of the CATE in our setting may be executed as follows

1. Split the data into K folds, repeating the process outlined below in Steps 2-4 on each of the training-validation splits in sequence, always performing any model fitting on a training fold and obtaining predictions only for the corresponding validation fold. We suppress notation to represent the folds for the sake of brevity.
2. Fit a super learner ensemble model to estimate $g_{A,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(A = 1 \mid L)$, the probability of receiving treatment (one of 9BLMZ, 9BCLLfzZ, 9BDLLfxZ); the super learner should include as candidate algorithms a subset of those specified above (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting) as well as the exact form of the logistic regression model used to compute $g_{A,n}$ for the IPW estimator. All covariates specified in the treatment confounder adjustment set should be included. Obtain predictions from the fitted ensemble model and denote these $g_{A,n}$. Obtain also the additive inverse of these predictions, $1 - g_{A,n}$ for each study unit.
3. Fit a super learner ensemble model to estimate $g_{C,n} = \mathbb{P}_n(C = 1 \mid A, L)$, the probability of completion (i.e., not being censored); the super learner should include as candidate algorithms a subset of those specified above (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting) as well as the exact form of the logistic regression model used to compute $g_{C,n}$ for the IPW estimator. All covariates specified in the censoring confounder adjustment set should be included. Obtain predictions from the fitted ensemble model and denote these $g_{C,n}$. For study units that are censored (i.e., $C = 0$), set their value of the outcome to zero; this will have no bearing on downstream estimation.
4. Subset the training set to only those units that are uncensored, i.e., for whom $C = 1$, and fit a super learner ensemble model to estimate $b_n(A, L)$, the conditional mean of the outcome (e.g., the conditional probability of recurrence-free survival); the super learner should include as candidate algorithms a subset of those specified above (e.g., random forests, gradient boosting). Only covariates specified in the treatment confounder adjustment set should be included. Obtain predictions from the fitted ensemble model for *all units in the validation set* (i.e., regardless of censoring status) on three distinct datasets: the observed data and two counterfactual datasets. To do so, obtain predictions on all (validation) units under their observed treatment status ($A = a$) as well as under two counterfactual scenarios, the first in which all units are set to the treatment condition ($A = 1$) and the second where all units are set to the control condition ($A = 0$), denoting these three sets of predictions by $b_n(a, L)$, $b_n(1, L)$, and $b_n(0, L)$, respectively.
5. At this stage, collect predictions for each of the nuisance parameters across all study units, collating predictions across the K validation sets, V_1, \dots, V_K , to have holdout predictions of each nuisance parameter, $(g_{A,n}, g_{C,n}, b_n(a, L), b_n(1, L), b_n(0, L))$, for each study unit. Now

construct the doubly robust pseudo-outcome for each study unit as

$$\tilde{Y}_{\text{DR}} = \frac{\mathbb{I}(C = 1)}{g_{C,n}} \frac{(A - g_{A,n})}{g_{A,n}(1 - g_{A,n})} \{Y - b_n(a, L)\} + (b_n(1, L) - b_n(0, L)) .$$

6. Regress the estimated pseudo-outcome \tilde{Y}_{DR} on putative effect modifiers V —that is, $\psi_{n,DR}^{\text{CATE}}(V) = \mathbb{E}_n[\tilde{Y}_{\text{DR}} | V]$ —and use the fitted regression to obtain predictions of the CATE, $\psi_{n,DR}^{\text{CATE}}(V)$ for all study units across all strata defined by V (i.e., PLHIV versus not).

While the DR-learner is a popular and well-studied choice for estimation of the CATE function $\psi_{\text{CATE}}(V)$, it suffers drawbacks of its own, most notably that it is based on a de-biased estimator of the risk of the CATE that may lead to a non-convex empirical risk, even in cases where the population risk is convex (Kennedy, 2023; van der Laan et al., 2024). Practical implications of this drawback include the fact that, when the outcome is binary (as in the present setting), the estimated CATE function derived from the DR-learner may output treatment effect estimates that fall outside of the closed interval $[-1, 1]$, which is highly undesirable given the fact that the true CATE function is bounded within this interval in such a case. Should this or related issues that compromise the performance of the DR-learner arise, we will consider implementation of an alternative approach, the EP-learner (van der Laan et al., 2024), which avoids the issue of a nonconvex loss by applying a data-adaptive sieve for debiasing; helpfully, Pryce et al. (2024) describe an implementation of the EP-learner in the setting where the outcome is subject to a censoring mechanism (see their Algorithm 2).

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